

Briefing on the ecological and societal impacts of wall construction at the Polish-Belarusian border

Wall Violates Legal Commitments

We, as scientists and EU citizens, are extremely concerned about the environmental and societal impacts arising from the walling and fencing off of the 418-kilometer Polish-Belarusian border. Border fencing began in late August 2021 with the construction of a provisional concertina wire fence. Border wall construction was initiated on 25th January, 2022 by the Polish Government without environmental impact assessment or public consultation. There is a lack of transparency and reliable information sharing about the details of the wall. According to the information we could gather, wall construction will include a 186km long and 5.5m high wall of concrete, steel, and razor wire along the terrestrial administrative boundary, and concertina wire fences along 232km of freshwater ecosystems and wetlands (Fig. 1). The wall violates commitments under EU Habitats Directives, EU Biodiversity Strategy, Bern Convention, the Convention on Biological Diversity, UNESCO World Heritage Convention and other international conservation agreements.

Fig. 1. Wall construction works across Białowieża Forest World Heritage Site and Biosphere Reserve (21st February 2022).

Wall sections bordering the Natura 2000 sites, in particular PLC200004 Białowieża Forest (Figs. 1, 2), should be subject to compulsory environmental impact assessment, in line with provisions of art. 6 of the EU Habitats Directive. Projects known to negatively affect the integrity of Natura 2000 sites cannot lawfully proceed unless there are no alternative ways of achieving the intended goals and unless they are justified by imperative reasons of overriding public interest. Validity of both these conditions should however be demonstrated as a part of a proper impact assessment procedure, rather than assumed a priori, as in this case. According to art. 6(4) of Habitats Directive, the competent national authorities are to authorise a project known to negatively affect the protected site only if they have made certain that alternative solutions are truly lacking and reasons for overriding public interests do apply. Even then, they can proceed only after appropriate compensatory measures are introduced and after the opinion of the European Commission has been voiced.

Wall Will Cause Irreversible Damage to Natura 2000 Sites

The Polish-Belarusian borderland encompasses natural habitats of enormous ecological value, including 9 Natura 2000 sites across 5 areas (Fig. 2). The Natura 2000 sites along Poland's eastern border include three large forests with considerable expanses of old growth: Augustów, Knyszyn, and Białowieża Forests. They also comprise the Biebrza Valley, Nadbużańska, and Bug River Valley sites (Fig. 2) with sensitive habitats such as marshes, peat bogs and oxbows, important not only for wildlife, but also for carbon sequestration.

Fig 2. Map showing the Natura 2000 network in NE Poland and the location of the Natura 2000 sites adjacent to the wall under construction along nearly half of the Polish-Belarusian border (418km).

These Natura 2000 sites form part of a coherent and interconnected network of protected areas whose conservation is critical to maintaining the functional and structural connectivity, as well as biodiversity, ecological processes and ecosystem resilience in Central and Eastern Europe. Sensitive habitats and species listed under the EU Birds and Habitats Directive will be disturbed during wall construction, maintenance and surveillance activities. The border wall will bisect 50km of the Białowieża Forest, a UNESCO transboundary World Heritage Site and Biosphere Reserve shared by Poland and Belarus and distinguished as Europe's last primeval forest. Of these 50km, 9.8km of wall will abut Białowieża National Park in Poland, with 5.7 km passing by the strictly protected core area. To our best knowledge, in forested areas, trees are already being cut, forest roads widened, and a maintenance road along the border belt is under construction. The wall impacts listed below will be cumulative, long-term and irreversible.

Wall Will Block Wildlife Movements and Gene Flow

The wall will become an impenetrable barrier to animal movement and gene flow, particularly of large mammals, which require expansive and connected habitats. Fragmented populations may experience stronger genetic drift and inbreeding, leading to the loss of genetic diversity and increasing the risk of local extinction over time, while being less resilient to disease and environmental change. NE Poland's Natura 2000 sites hold important populations of large mammals such as wolf, Eurasian lynx, European bison, and moose. The moose population in NE Poland is at the border of the species range and genetically unique, whereas the bison population is the largest and most important for the species conservation. Genetic studies on red deer have shown that the existing Belarusian fence was permeable and dispersal between the two sides of the Białowieża Forest was documented.

The lowland eastern wolf population has been key to the recolonization process and formation of the central European wolf population and data reveal that genetic flow has existed and that individual GPS-tracked wolves successfully dispersed across the Belarusian fence (Fig. 3). Brown bears just started to naturally recolonize Białowieża Forest from Belarusian forests, a process that the new wall will halt completely on the Polish side. The lynx population in NE Poland already has extremely low genetic variability, despite the dispersal and movement across the existing Belarusian fence revealed by GPS-tracked lynx in 2008-2012 (Fig. 3). The new wall will block lynx movement and gene flow completely, thus affecting the population connectivity and seriously compromising the conservation status of the NE Poland lynx population in the long-term. It has been documented that concertina wire fences, already established and planned to be used along the border, cause serious injury and death to wildlife (Fig. 4). Their impact on wildlife mortality may be particularly strong at river banks and during seasonal flooding, such as typifies the Bug River Valley.

Fig. 3. Large carnivore GPS-telemetry conducted in Białowieża Forest has recorded (A) Eurasian lynx border crossings across the Belarusian fence (data from the Mammal Research Institute PAS, 2008-2012), and (B) long-distance dispersal of wolves towards the west across the same fence; one of these individuals successfully bred in Central Poland after dispersing from its natal area (data from the Frankfurt Zoological Society, 20017-2018).

Wall Will Fragment Habitats and Increase Human Disturbance

Habitat fragmentation is one of the main threats for the conservation of wildlife and ecosystems worldwide. Loss of trees and vegetation cover associated with wall construction will exacerbate ecosystem fragmentation. An access road is being constructed along the border and small forest roads are experiencing a significant increase in traffic, particularly of heavy vehicles. These roads and more frequent traffic are affecting largely undisturbed natural areas and are linked to soil erosion and compaction; chemical, noise and light pollution; risk of potential spills from machinery; increased fire risk; and road mortality of

amphibians, reptiles, arthropods, birds, and mammals. These impacts will be particularly negative during wall construction, which is also happening during nighttime, thus disturbing crepuscular and nocturnal wildlife and the sensitive breeding season, which began on 1st March, an aspect neglected by investors and authorities. Fragmented and human-disturbed areas are more prone to invasions by nonnative plant species, seeds of which are carried on shoes, vehicle tires or construction materials. Species invasions are extremely difficult to control once they have entered an ecosystem. This is of special concern in Białowieża Forest, which has mostly evaded such invasions.

Fig. 4. Red deer entangled and dead due to injuries at concertina fence placed at the Polish border in Białowieża Forest, September 2021.

Wall Has Negative Social Effects

The decision to build a solid barrier along the border with Belarus by the Polish Government did not take local communities into account, nor the social consequences. In its current shape, the wall will reduce the attractiveness of the region for tourism, particularly for nature and wildlife tourism, an important source of income. The militarized border zone undermines to-date investment in nature-based tourism and affects tourism potential in the future. Local people, visitors and researchers are excluded from extensive “no-go” zones, affecting recreation and research, and avoiding documentation of wall effects. Local economies and sources of income of inhabitants running businesses in the tourism sector will suffer. The construction of the wall at the Polish-Belarusian border was not preceded with any consultations with the local communities or with relevant experts. The wall will also thwart positive global momentum of transboundary cooperation in research and conservation, for example EU rewilding efforts.

Experiences with border walls in other parts of the world are generally negative. They divide local communities and increase distrust and even hostility; at the same time, they only give an illusory, subjective and short-lived sense of security. International experiences (such as from the United States-Mexican or Israeli-Palestinian borders) show that border walls do not prevent illegal border crossings; former U.S. secretary of homeland security Janet Napolitano famously said, “Show me a 50-foot wall, and I’ll show you a 51-foot ladder”. Data from Frontex¹ show that despite the operation of physical fences at the border, migration through the Western Balkans route has been growing recently. Moreover, the existence of physical barriers promotes the development of a network of smugglers and criminal groups aimed at helping migrants cross the border illegally. These groups are often brutal in their activities, which hurts the sense of security and safety of border communities and endangers especially migrant women and children.

The costs of wall construction are estimated at 1.6 billion PLN (about 336 million euro). Such allocation of funds has no rational or ethical justification as the wall will not deter human migration while causing costly social and environmental harms. Given the current war and humanitarian crisis in Ukraine, this money may be better spent on humanitarian assistance and modern equipment and technologies for border monitoring.

Wall Will Scar Northeast Poland & Central-Eastern Europe

The ecological integrity and resilience of the Natura 2000 network will be seriously jeopardized by this wall. The wall constitutes one of Poland’s largest single infrastructure projects, and will cast an enormous footprint on the region. Northeastern Poland is a land of forests, marshes, meadows, riverine habitats and peaceful countryside and represents one of the best-preserved natural regions in Europe. The integrity of the landscape, conservation status of flora and fauna, and health and well-being of human inhabitants are at stake.

The border wall will cross ecological corridors of pan-European importance, crucial for the preservation of forest, freshwater and wetland habitats in Central Europe and for maintaining the ecological connectivity between eastern and western Europe. Avoiding habitat fragmentation and maintaining ecological connectivity are of paramount importance for biodiversity conservation, climate change adaptation, and disaster risk reduction. Transboundary regions often overlap with biocultural hotspots and conservation priority areas, and act as refuges for wildlife, endemic and threatened species. The detrimental effects of wall construction on biodiversity will intersect with other ongoing human impacts, such as logging, road building, and urban sprawl. Moreover, Poland’s border wall impacts will be cumulative and act in combination with similar border barriers under construction in Lithuania and Latvia, and with Belarus’s existing 2m-high fence, developed in the 1980s. The scale of linear barrier effects will be continental and long-term.

¹ <https://frontex.europa.eu/media-centre/news/news-release/situation-at-eu-s-external-borders-in-january-lower-pressure-on-eastern-border-gAuRpK>

Wall Construction Should Be Immediately Halted

Without evaluating environmental and social impacts, and designing careful mitigation and compensation measures, in consultation with communities and experts, the wall will have irreversible negative impacts. We therefore call for the suspension of the construction works of Poland's wall at the border with Belarus until a proper assessment required by art. 6 of the Habitats Directive is carried out and local border communities and stakeholders are duly consulted.

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